

4D/RCS Sensory Processing and World Modeling on the Demo III Experimental Unmanned Ground Vehicles

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Abstract – The success of the Army Research Lab Demo III project at Ft. Indiantown Gap in November, 2001 suggests that autonomous driving by unmanned ground vehicles under tactical conditions is achievable within this decade. Laser range imaging sensors have been developed to provide dense range images that enable autonomous vehicles to build an internal geometric model of the terrain and objects within the environment. Real-time value-based planning algorithms have been developed that enable the autonomous vehicle to replan its intended path through the environment many times per second. The 4D/RCS system architecture has been validated as an open, modular, hierarchical, multi-resolutional integration architecture and design methodology for unmanned ground vehicles.

Index Terms—Unmanned ground vehicles, sensory processing, world modeling, 4D/RCS

I. INTRODUCTION

During November of 2001, the Demo III program under the leadership of the Army Research Lab performed a series of autonomous cross-country driving experiments and unmanned scout missions at Ft. Indiantown Gap, PA. [1, 2] During these experiments the Demo III Experimental Unmanned Ground Vehicles (XUVs) were operated by soldiers from Ft. Hood and Ft. Indiantown Gap. A video of the November demonstration is available from the Demo III program office at the Aberdeen Proving Grounds in Aberdeen, MD. [3]

The experiments at Ft. Indiantown Gap were designed to demonstrate a series of capabilities that include stealthy off-road movement, reconnaissance, surveillance, target acquisition, road-following, leader-follower, and smoke operations. The missions were planned using a standard military map displayed on a touch-screen operator control unit. Soldiers were able to plan simultaneous missions for up to four autonomous vehicles. The missions were typically one kilometer or more in length across rough hilly terrain that often took the robot vehicles beyond line of sight from the control unit. The vehicles were able to maneuver autonomously at tactical speeds through tall

grass, weeds, woods, brush, stumps, fallen trees, ditches, and mud. This performance was enabled by four factors:

1. LADAR – Laser range imagers have been developed that can produce range images, i.e., images in which each pixel provides a range value.
2. World Modeling – A multiresolutional approach has been developed that makes it possible to build a geometric representation of the terrain and dynamic objects in the world in real-time.
3. Processing speed – Modern PCs have sufficient computational power to update the world model and perform a path planning search of a cost map registered with the terrain five times per second.
4. System architecture – Software for the Demo III vehicles was integrated in the 4D/RCS reference model architecture for intelligent ground vehicles. [4, 5, 6]

Section II provides an overview of the 4D/RCS architecture developed for the Demo III program. Section III describes the sensing system and the algorithms used to extract information necessary for driving. Section IV briefly outlines the hierarchical world model where sensory data is combined with a priori knowledge and represented in a form that can be used for planning and decision making. Section V discusses the implications of the Demo III experience. Section VI outlines issues for future work.

II. THE 4D/RCS ARCHITECTURE

A high-level block diagram of the first five levels in the 4D/RCS architecture for Demo III is shown in Figure 1 (at the end of this paper.) On the right, Behavior Generation modules decompose high level mission commands into low level actions. The text inside the Planner at each level indicates the planning horizon at each level. Each planner has a world model simulator that is appropriate for the problems encountered at its level. In the center, is the world model knowledge database consisting of maps, images, and symbolic data structures (or frames.) Each map as a range and resolution that is appropriate for path planning at its level. The frames describe attributes, state, and class of entities and events and contain pointers that define relationships between them. Also in the center, are

coordinate transformations that transform geometric data from image to map coordinates, and vice versa. On the left, is a sensory processing hierarchy that extracts information from the sensory data stream that is needed to keep the world model knowledge database current and accurate.

At the bottom are actuators that act on the world and sensors that measure phenomena in the world. The Demo III vehicles have a variety of sensors including a laser range imager (LADAR), stereo CCD (charge coupled device) cameras, stereo forward looking infra red (FLIR) devices, a color CCD, GPS (Global Positioning System), an inertial navigation package, actuator feedback sensors, and a variety of internal sensors for measuring parameters such as engine temperature, speed, vibration, oil pressure, and fuel level. The vehicles also carry a Reconnaissance, Surveillance, and Target Acquisition (RSTA) mission package that includes long-range cameras and FLIRs, a laser range finder, and an acoustic package.

In Figure 1, the Servo level has no map representation. The Servo level deals with actuator dynamics and reacts to sensory feedback from actuator sensors. The Primitive level map has range of 5 m with resolution of 4 cm. This enables the vehicle to make small path corrections to avoid bumps and ruts during the 500 ms planning horizon of the Primitive level. The Primitive level also uses accelerometer data to measure terrain roughness for speed control.

The Subsystem level map has range of 50 m with resolution of 40 cm. This map is used to plan about 5 s into the future to find a path that avoids obstacles and provides a smooth and efficient ride. The Vehicle level map has a range of 500 m with resolution of 4 m. This map is used to plan paths about one minute into the future taking into account terrain features such as roads, bushes, gullies, or tree lines. The Section level map has a range of 5000 m with resolution of 40 m. This map can be used to plan about 10 minutes into the future to accomplish tactical behaviors. Higher level maps (not shown in Figure 1) will be used to plan section and platoon missions lasting about 2 and 24 hours respectively. These are derived from a priori military maps.

III. LADAR SENSING

As the beam of the LADAR scans over the egosphere, it generates an image consisting of pixels wherein each pixel has a location (or address) of u and v , where u = bearing and v = elevation, and each pixel has an attribute of range r . u and v are determined by the position of the laser beam, and r is determined by the time delay of the reflected laser pulse. The LADAR image thus consists of a cloud of points in 3-D space represented in polar (or egosphere) coordinates. These 3-D points can be easily transformed into x , y , z coordinates in vehicle centered world map coordinates. Registration with a priori maps requires knowledge of the vehicle position that is derived from a

Global Position System (GPS) receiver and an Inertial Navigation System (INS).

The LADAR used by the Demo III vehicles generates range images such as shown in Figure 2b. Range images can be overlaid with color images such as shown in Figure 2a. The fusion of range and color data facilitates segmentation and classification of regions and objects in the image. Both range and color discontinuities can be used as segmentation cues. Shape, size, color, and texture can serve as classification criteria.

Figure 2. A color image (a) and LADAR image (b) of a bend in the road. The position of the vehicle where the LADAR image was taken is indicated in the LADAR image.

Obstacles are defined as objects that project more than a given distance above or below the ground plane (defined as the plane on which the wheels of the vehicle lie). Positive obstacles, which extend above the ground plane, are detected in the range image. [7] A pixel is labeled as belonging to a positive obstacle if it rises high enough and abruptly enough from the ground plane.

Negative obstacles are detected in the world model map. A negative obstacle detection algorithm operates on a terrain elevation map of the ground centered on the vehicle. This map contains all the projected ground pixels detected in the range image. The algorithm identifies groups of pixels in the range image that are far enough below the ground level and large enough [8] to be hazardous for the vehicle to drive into.

After a group of pixels has been labeled as an obstacle, additional processing is performed to classify the obstacle type. The approach is based on the method of Ojala, Pietikäinen, and Harwood⁷. It makes use of two texture measures, Local Binary Patterns (LBP), and Contrast. The LBP values are combined with a contrast measure at each point, computed over the same 3_3 window. The contrast measure is computed as the difference between the averages of the range values of the pixels with ranges greater than the center pixel and those with ranges less than the center pixel value. This range contrast can be viewed as a measure of porosity of a volume. If the volume is sparsely filled, the contrast will be large, as in the case of grass. If the foliage is denser, such as for brush or thick shrubs, the contrast will

be smaller, since the expected distance the laser will travel before hitting a surface will decrease. If the surface is solid, the contrast should be close to zero.

The texture measures were computed after the obstacles were identified. First, the connected components of the obstacle image are found. For each obstacle, a two-dimensional histogram is computed from the texture measures applied to the pixels in the component. The histogram is used to determine the class to which the obstacle belongs. Classes are defined by class prototypes that are created during a learning phase.

IV. WORLD MODEL

The world model is the system's internal representation of the external world. It provides a central repository for storing sensory data in a unified representation, and decouples the real-time sensory updates from the rest of the system. [10] The world model process has two primary functions:

1. To create a knowledge database (map) and keep it current and consistent. In this role, it updates existing data in accordance with inputs from the sensors, and deletes information no longer believed to be representative of the world. It also assigns confidence factors to all map data and adjusts these factors as new data are sensed. The types of information included in the world model are state variables (e.g., time, position, orientation), system parameters (e.g., coordinate transforms, sensor to vehicle offsets, etc.), and lists or classes of sensed objects. The world model process also provides functions to update and fuse data and to manage the map (e.g. scrolling and grouping objects.)
2. To generate predictions based on the current state of the world and estimated future states of the world. For the Demo III autonomous driving application, very little *a priori* information is available at the highest resolution in the hierarchy to support path planning between the vehicle's position and a final goal position. The world model therefore constructs and maintains all the information necessary for intelligent path planning. [11, 12] At lower resolution levels, *a priori* information is supplied from maps of the area being modeled.

The world model includes a set of maps at multiple levels of resolution. The Autonomous Mobility (AM) level maintains a model of the area around the vehicle (a map) to 50 m from the vehicle, at a resolution of 40 cm per map cell. The sensory processing that takes place at this level combines information from multiple imaging sensors to construct and maintain the map. The map is used by a path planner to develop plans for vehicle motion out to about 50 m, with an update rate of about 5 Hz. An example of an AM level map is shown in Figure 3.

The level above the AM level in the 4D/RCS hierarchy is the Vehicle Level. This level of the hierarchy contains a

world model and behavior generation system that operates over a larger extent and lower resolution than the AM level. The level has a cycle time on the order of seconds instead of milliseconds, and operates on a map with a cell size of 5 m and an extent of 500 m.

Figure 3. A display of the terrain map used by the Demo III path planner. The geometry of the road and surrounding foliage can be seen. The vehicle's current position is shown in the map with the current path plan shown as a string of waypoints ahead of the vehicle. The faint lines at the right show the current field of view of the LADAR

The Vehicle Level world model includes feature and elevation data from a priori digital terrain maps. For example, information about roads, bridges, streams, woods, buildings may be contained in a priori maps. This information is registered and merged with data from the AM level maps that are generated by sensors.

Both the AM and Vehicle level maps are north oriented and scroll as the vehicle moves. On both maps, features are integrated over time, confidence levels are computed so as to filter out spurious obstacles.

The primary use of the model data is to plan safe and efficient paths at each level of resolution. For each planning cycle, a copy of the obstacle map is rotated from a north-oriented into a vehicle-oriented map and is sent to the planner. The path-planning module uses the map to select a locally optimal path from the current position to the commanded goal. For example, the highest resolution planner heuristically selects a path by starting with a web of potential path segments that extend out 20 m. The path is updated (replanned) approximately ten times per second³. There are two types of potential path segments: straight and curved. Curved segments extend from the vehicle to the outer edge of the Primitive level map. At the Primitive level, each potential path is a series of clothoid segments that are kinematically feasible based on the turn rate of the steering wheel. These potential paths are generated offline for different initial speeds and steering wheel positions.

Potential straight path segments are used for the AM level planner to generate plans out to 50 m away from the vehicle. Although not kinematically feasible, they are computationally simpler. Given that the path plan is recomputed frequently, an exact solution for more distant segments is not necessary.

At each level, the planner selects the best combination of segments leading toward the goal, using a cost function depending on its task. It does this by first pruning all segments blocked by obstacles. Then it searches through the remaining segments to find the path with lowest cost. Among the factors used in the cost function are terrain elevation, the presence or absence of obstacles, tree cover, the presence of tall grass areas, the relative distance between different path options, and commanded speed.

It is in this map representation that the planner operates. The planner developed at NIST for the Demo III program can find an optimal path in this terrain map in less than 50 milliseconds. [11] This makes it possible for the Demo III vehicles to process the lidar image, update the map, and generate a new plan 5 times per second. The 4D/RCS architecture organizes all these various functions into a system design that is modular, open, and amenable to being scaled up to higher levels and more complex environments.

V. DISCUSSION

The success of the Army Research Lab Demo III project at Ft. Indiantown Gap in November, 2001 suggests that autonomous driving by unmanned ground vehicles under tactical conditions may be achievable within a decade, and almost certainly can be achieved within two decades. The reasons for making this prediction are as follows:

1. The sensor technology to support autonomous driving will be available. LADAR is a critical break-through. The ability of LADAR to sense range images directly enables the vehicle to build a geometrical model of the terrain in real time.
2. The fundamental technologies of sensing, perception, representation, decision, planning, control are understood in principle. Once the geometry of the world can be computed, segmentation, classification, and logical reasoning about the world become well defined.
3. The computing power to implement these technologies will be available. Computational power per unit cost is growing by a factor of 10 every five years. This is two orders of magnitude per decade, and four orders of magnitude within two decades.
4. The 4D/RCS reference model architecture provides a means for integrating these fundamental technologies into an intelligent system. In particular, Demo III demonstrated that:
 - a) Path planning can be performed fast enough to react to unexpected changes in a dynamic world.

- b) A rich world model can be constructed and updated often enough to support dynamic path planning.
- c) LADAR sensors can produce a depth image of the world fast enough to maintain a rich dynamic world model.
- d) Data from sensors can be fused with a priori information to generate intelligent behavior.

VI. FUTURE WORK

The Demo III experience also pointed up some of the factors limiting performance in autonomous driving. One of the most important of these is the lack of resolution in the depth image. The current LADAR has a resolution of only about 0.5 degrees per pixel. The human fovea has a resolution of about 0.02 degrees per pixel, i.e., a factor of 25 times better resolution. In other words, the resolving power of the human eye is 25 times better than that of the LADAR.

On-road driving requires the detection, classification, and tracking of objects the size of small automobiles at a range of 200 m. It requires the ability to read road signs and traffic signals at a range of 50 m. It requires the ability to detect and classify pedestrians and animals, and to measure their position, orientation, and velocity at a range of 30 m. It requires the ability to identify and understand hand gestures given by traffic police at a range of 10 m. Driving in traffic requires the ability to detect and track other vehicles and moving objects approaching from the front, side, or back. Vehicles approaching from the front, need to be detected and tracked within a range of about 200 m. Vehicles approaching from the side, or back need to be detected and tracked within a range of 50 m.

Off-road driving requires the sensors and sensory processing system to detect and measure the position, size, and shape of objects such as trees, stumps, logs, rocks, and embankments, and to estimate the slope of the ground out to distance of about 40 m. The sensor system must be able to measure the roughness of the terrain and to detect and characterize ruts, ditches, and gullies at a distance of 5 to 10 m. Off-road driving requires the ability to pan and tilt cameras to compensate for roll, pitch, and yaw of the vehicle as it moves over undulating terrain. It may require mechanical or electronic image stabilization to compensate for terrain-induced vibration.

There are two issues here: One is how to determine what constitutes an object of interest, and the second is how best to track objects of interest. Top down, objects of interest are objects that are relevant to the system goals. Bottom-up object of interest are those that are unexpected, peculiar, or dangerous. Tracking objects of interest requires that sensors be designed to have both wide angle (peripheral vision) and narrow angle (foveal vision) fields of view. This implies that the vision sensors should be

mounted on a pan/tilt head that can enable it to point its cameras in a commanded direction relative to the vehicle coordinate frame. The foveal sensors must be stabilized and be capable of saccadic motion to points of attention. The foveal sensors must be able to track moving targets with nearly the speed and precision of human vision, and generate about 4 saccades per second between targets that are less than 10 degrees apart in the image. The peripheral fields should be designed to be sensitive to image flow.

The UGV vision sensor suite should include wrap-around sensors that cover 360 degrees in azimuth. These should be capable of measuring the position and velocity of objects within a range of 50 m of the vehicle from the sides or back. The vision sensor suite should also include sensors that measure the position, intensity, and color of the sun and other ambient illumination, and the brightness distribution of the sky.

Finally, the UGV vision sensor suite must be rugged and reliable under extremely harsh environmental conditions. The ability to produce a vision system that can meet these requirements will be critical to the development of autonomous vehicles with tactical military capabilities.

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VIII. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Five levels of the 4-D/RCS architecture. On the right, are Planner and Executor modules. In the middle, are maps for representing terrain features, road, bridges, vehicles, friendly/enemy positions, and the cost and risk of traversing various regions. On the left, are Sensory Processing functions, symbolic representations of entities and events, and segmented images with labeled regions.